

Optimized feature pattern for the advancement of an automatic pain recognition system

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Abstract—In the future, automatic pain monitoring may enable health care professionals to assess and manage pain objectively. In this framework, the researchers created a database of biopotentials for the development of an automatic pain-recognition system and the optimization of its performance. The goal of the current research work was to optimize pain features with a Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier and to obtain high recognition rates for pain quantification in a two- and multiclass problem. Data of 90 participants were acquired under the induction of phasic heat pain stimulation. 13 features were finally selected from the following categories: amplitude, stationarity, linearity, variability and similarity. Classification analyses were performed with a SVM for four classification problems (baseline vs. pain threshold; baseline vs. pain tolerance; pain threshold vs. pain tolerance; baseline vs. pain threshold vs. pain tolerance). High classification accuracies were obtained for baseline vs. pain threshold (80 %) and baseline vs. pain tolerance (91 %). This study is the first to indicate one distinct set of features which successfully differentiated a no pain condition from different pain intensities. Thus, the detection of pain patterns via an automatic pain-recognition system in clinical settings is feasible more than ever before because of the small number of physiological parameters and features.

Keywords—Pain, heat stimulation, biopotentials, feature selection, Support Vector Machine, pain recognition

I. INTRODUCTION

In clinical and care home settings, accurate assessment of pain is essential for successful pain management. A failure to recognize and treat pain can lead to health problems and unacceptable suffering. For instance, the lack of sufficient pain management is associated with pathophysiological effects, such as increased blood pressure and heart rate [1]. In general, valid and reliable pain assessment is necessary to facilitate successful pain management without complications and enhance quality of life [2].

To date, self-reporting is the standard method for assessing pain but requires the capacity to comprehend the task and to communicate about the experienced pain [3]. This implies that self-report scales are not always a valid and reliable tool for assessing pain, especially in those who have verbal or cognitive impairments. Although there are pain observation assessment tools for people with cognitive impairment or for

non-communicative older adults, most of these methods are highly complex and demand specialized experts [4]. Moreover, comprehensive pain assessment should be regularly repeated, particularly if the individual is not able to communicate. The systematic and accurate pain assessment via observation tools may be a challenging and time-consuming task for healthcare providers' clinical routine.

To the best of authors' knowledge, the study by Brahnham et al. [5] was the first one that focused on automated pain detection based on neonatal facial images of pain. To date, there are numerous research works in the field of computer vision [6-8]. Furthermore, previous studies have examined the correlation between a single biopotential and pain [9-16]. However, in conventional pain diagnostics, it is well known that a measurement of a single parameter is insufficient for valid and precise diagnosis. Instead, a combination of multiple features is required [17]. The study by Treister et al. [18] was the first one that adopted a multiparameter approach for discriminating heat pain intensities. A linear combination of bio parameters significantly differentiated between pain vs. no pain and also between all pain conditions.

The researchers aim at the advancement of pain monitoring and the assessment of different pain conditions. A machine learning model (based on Support Vector Machine; SVM) could be the solution for an effective and precise pain assessment. According to Brown et al. [19], "An SVM Model could be trained on one set of individuals and used to accurately classify pain in different individuals" (p. 2). In this context, Gruss et al. [20] developed a dataset incorporating a set of different physiological parameters - i.e., cardiac electrical activity, facial and trapezius muscle activity, and skin conductance - under the induction of several pain levels and performed SVM classifications combined with feature selection algorithms so as to determine valid feature sets for two- and multiclass problems. They obtained high recognition rates based on different feature sets for each classification task.

The goal of the present study is to optimize the classification rates achieved by Gruss et al. [20] by ranking the previous selected features by the frequency of their appearance and developing one distinct optimal feature set with a SVM learning design that fits each pain classification task.

II. EXPERIMENTAL AND COMPUTATIONAL DETAILS

A. Participants

A total of 90 participants participated in the experiment belonging to the following age groups: a) 18-35 years (N=30 years; 15 females, 15 males), b) 36-50 years (N=30; 15 females, 15 males), and c) 51-65 years (N=30; 15 females, 15 males). Data from four participants had to be omitted due to limited electromyography data quality, leaving 86 participants for further analysis.

B. Heat Pain Calibration

A Medoc Pathway thermal stimulator was employed to elicit heat pain. An ATS thermode was applied to the upper side of the forearm of the participant. During the entire experiment, participants were seated in a chair with their arm resting on the desk in front of them. At the beginning of the experimental session the researchers calibrated the individual pain threshold (T_1) and pain tolerance (T_4) for each participant: The researchers performed four measurements for T_1 and T_4 , respectively. Afterwards an average value was calculated for T_1 and T_4 . Subsequently, the researchers utilized T_1 and T_4 pain levels to calculate two additional intermediate levels (T_2 , T_3) so as to obtain a ranged set of four equally distributed pain levels. These four pain levels (T_1 , T_2 , T_3 and T_4) were then used for the main part (= heat pain stimulation) of the experiment.

C. Heat Pain Stimulation

During the main experimental phase each of the four individualized stimuli was randomly applied 20 times, resulting in a total of 80 stimuli. The Baseline (B) temperature (= no pain) was 32 °C. Each pain stimulus was performed for 4 s. The pauses between the stimuli were randomized between 8-12 s. Participants were told that they are able to leave the experiment at any time by pressing the emergency stop button. At the end of the experiment, participants were requested to apply a cold compress to the area of heat pain stimulation for at least 5 min.

D. Measured Physiological Parameters

A Nexus-32 amplifier was utilized to record biopotential data, which sampled physiological channels at 2048 Hz. Biopotentials and event data were recorded using the Biotrace software. The following psychophysiological signals were included in the classification process [21]:

1) *Electromyography (EMG)*: Three Ag/AgCl single electrodes were utilized to quantify muscle activity of the right upper *trapezius* muscle. Two electrodes were placed on a straight line from the spine of the 7th cervical vertebra (C7) to the lateral edge of acromion spanning the midpoint between the two landmarks [22]. The reference electrode was placed on the C7 spinous process. Furthermore, bipolar pairs of Ag/AgCl electrodes were utilized for measuring facial EMG activity. The electrodes were placed over the left *corrugator supercilii* and *zygomaticus major* muscles. Electrical muscle activity indicates general psychophysiological arousal [20]. In particular, a high level of muscle tension is an indicator of stress [23], which is also expected to occur under the experience of pain [20, 21].

2) *Skin Conductance Level (SCL)*: Skin conductance is a measure of the conductivity of the skin, which especially increases if the skin becomes sweaty. Two electrodes were positioned on the volar pads of the distal phalanges of the left index and ring finger to measure SCL. Electrodermal

activity is considered to be a sensitive indicator of the inner tension of an individual.

3) *Electrocardiography (ECG)*: Three single Ag/AgCl electrodes were utilized to measure the average cardiac action potential on the skin. One electrode was placed below the right clavicle, the second electrode was placed on the left lower rib cage. The reference electrode was the same one which served as reference for EMG of the *trapezius* muscle. Common features of the ECG signal are heart rate, interbeat interval and heart rate variability (HRV). Heart rate reflects emotional activity [23], whereas HRV refers to the oscillation of the interval between consecutive heartbeats and acts as an indicator of mental effort and stress.

E. Signal Processing and Feature Extraction

A band-pass Butterworth filter was applied to filter raw EMG (20-250 Hz) and ECG (0.1-250 Hz) signals. The researchers employed additional processing methods for EMG signals, namely the Empirical Mode Decomposition technique [24] and the Hilbert Spectrum [25]. No filter was applied to the raw SCL signals because of high quality. In order to quantify pain levels, the researchers defined *pain-windows* of 5.5 s during pain induction and *non-pain windows* (B) of 5.5 s during the pauses, respectively (see Fig. 1).

The researchers systematically extracted features from the mathematical groups of *amplitude* ($\Sigma=40$), *frequency* ($\Sigma=24$), *stationarity* ($\Sigma=24$), *entropy* ($\Sigma=20$), *linearity* ($\Sigma=8$), *variability* ($\Sigma=19$) and *similarity* ($\Sigma=24$) (in total: $\Sigma=159$). A comprehensive description of all the extracted features is provided by Gruss et al. [20].

F. Classification Process

Prior to the classification process, each extracted feature was standardized (z-transformed) per person. Classification was performed with a SVM classifier as they have been proven to be highly effective in affective computing research [26], and have the ability to maintain sufficient flexibility with regard to their internal main parameter optimization [27]. More information on the classification method can be found elsewhere [20].

G. Feature Selection

The researchers performed SVM classifications in conjunction with a Sequential Forward Selection (SFS) to determine individual feature sets for each classification task. All SVM classifiers were trained on 75 % of data and tested on the remaining 25 % of data (see Gruss et al. [20] for more

Fig. 1. Example of a pain-window of 5.5 s during pain stimulation and B (non-pain window), respectively.

information). The number of hereby-obtained features ranged from 5 to 22 (depending on learning/classification task).

H. Validity of Classification Rates

In published research works that address classification tasks, classification results are widely presented without a measure of validity, such as the level of significance in conventional statistics. However, the researchers strongly believe that a measure of validity should be included in future analyses. In the current study, they chose *Cramér's V* as an appropriate measure because it measures the strength of association between nominal variables. The value of *Cramér's V* ranges from 0 to +1 and is interpreted as follows: $V < 0.1$: negligible association, $0.1 < V < 0.2$: weak association, $0.2 < V < 0.4$: moderate association, $0.4 < V < 0.6$: relatively strong association, $0.6 < V < 0.8$: strong association, and $0.8 < V \leq 1$: very strong association [28].

III. RESULTS

A. Summary of the Previously Published Results

In the researchers' previously published study, different sets of features were selected for each classification task. The classification rates for two-class problems ranged between 74.11-90.94 %. Particularly, classification accuracy for B vs. $T1$ was 79.29 % ($V=0.59$), whereas the highest classification rate was achieved for B vs. $T4$ (90.94 %; $V=0.82$). Classification rates for the other two-class problems were slightly below or above chance level. Classification accuracy was 73.09 % ($V=0.62$) for a three-class problem (B vs. $T1$ vs. $T4$) and 43.05 % ($V=0.38$) for a five-class problem (B vs. $T1$ vs. $T2$ vs. $T3$ vs. $T4$).

B. Results of the Current Study

According to the researchers of the current study, a differentiation between B , $T1$ and $T4$ seems more relevant in clinical practice than the differentiation between the intermediate levels ($T2$, $T3$). Therefore, they only included B , $T1$ and $T4$ in the new classification processes.

Furthermore, a distinct set of features that fits each pain level classification may be the solution for the successful assessment of pain in clinical settings. For this purpose, researchers decided to rank the selected features by the frequency of appearance of each feature. All features which appeared minimum two times in the feature ranking were included in a new feature set. Finally, the new feature set consisted of 13 features, namely *Top-13-Features*, which then was utilized for the following pain classification tasks: 1) B vs. $T1$, 2) B vs. $T4$, 3) $T1$ vs. $T4$ and 4) B vs. $T1$ vs. $T4$.

Table I presents an overview of the employed features for each selected biosignal. A detailed description and calculation of all features can be found in [20]. The *Top-13-Features* derived from the following categories: *amplitude* ($\Sigma=4$), *stationarity* ($\Sigma=1$), *linearity* ($\Sigma=1$), *variability* ($\Sigma=1$) and *similarity* ($\Sigma=6$). Classification analyses were performed with a SVM classifier for the above mentioned four classification tasks. The SVM model was trained on 75% of the data and tested on the remaining unseen 25% of the data.

Fig. 2 displays classification rates for the four classification tasks based on the *Top-13-Features* and classification rates for the corresponding classification tasks based on the individually selected feature sets from the previous study of Gruss et al. [20]. Notably, the same or similarly high classification accuracies were obtained for B vs. $T1$ (80 %, $V=0.58$) and B vs. $T4$ (91 %, $V=0.82$) compared with the previous results.

TABLE I. COMPLETE LIST OF THE TOP-13-FEATURES

Nr.	Feature	Biosignal	Category
1	root mean square	EMG zygomaticus	Amplitude
2	lag dependence function	EMG zygomaticus	Linearity
3	correlation	EMG zygomaticus	Similarity
4	standard deviation of the mean values	EMG zygomaticus	Stationarity
5	variance	EMG zygomaticus	Variability
6	peak	EMG corrugator	Amplitude
7	correlation	EMG corrugator	Similarity
8	mutual information	EMG corrugator	Similarity
9	correlation	EMG trapezius	Similarity
10	mutual information	EMG trapezius	Similarity
11	peak to peak mean value	SCL	Amplitude
12	peak	SCL	Amplitude
13	correlation	SCL	Similarity

Fig. 2. Classification rates for the corresponding classification tasks based on the selected feature sets from the study of Gruss et al. [20] and the four classification tasks based on the *Top-13-Features*.

For $T1$ vs. $T4$, the classification rate was higher for the *Top-13-Features* (76.47 %, $V=0.53$) than the classification rate achieved for the previously selected features (74.11 %, $V=0.48$), whereas the classification rate for the three-class-problem (71.84 %, $V=0.60$) was lower than the one obtained for the previous three-class-problem.

IV. DISCUSSION

The goal of the current research work was to select only one distinct feature set from an existing dataset [20] to obtain high and valid recognition rates for pain quantification in a two- and multiclass problem. To reduce computational feature selection effort, the researchers decided to rank the features obtained by Gruss et al. [20] and to utilize only features that appeared minimum two times. The researchers are well-aware that a different selection method e.g., brute-force feature selection, would have been a better solution. However, this method would require a non-tolerable excessive amount of computational time.

The results of the current study demonstrated that *no pain* and pain levels $T1$ and $T4$ can be successfully discriminated based on a remarkably small number of physiological parameters by a SVM classifier, outperforming the results from the published study by Gruss et al. [20]. Furthermore, the relatively high increase in classification accuracy for $T1$ vs. $T4$ is noteworthy. Although the recognition rate for the three-class-problem was lower than the classification rate achieved

by Gruss et al. [20], still a very similar accuracy was obtained. To the best of authors' knowledge, this study is the first to indicate a distinct set of features which successfully differentiated no pain condition from *T1* and *T4*. Additionally, the small number of physiological parameters and features decreases the computational effort extremely, which is an important factor for online classification in real-time.

The researchers plan to advance the present study with the following aspects:

1) Conducting new experiments to test and improve the generalizability with complex pain models including phasic (short lasting) and tonic (longer lasting) pain, heat, pressure, and electrocutaneous pain stimulation.

2) Testing and validating an automatic pain-recognition system in a postoperative setting of a clinic and in a care unit for people with dementia.

Finally, the research group advances towards its vision of an automatic pain-recognition system by utilizing multimodal sensor technology and highly effective data classification systems that will facilitate precise pain assessment in patients in clinical and care home settings. The accurate pain assessment via machine learning algorithms will provide healthcare professionals with valuable information about patients' medical conditions to enable effective personalized management of pain without complications and deliver a higher quality of patient care.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Michael Serpell (Ed.). 2008. Handbook of pain management. Springer, New York. DOI: 10.1007/978-1-908517-12-8
- [2] H. McQuay, A. Moore, and D. Justins. 1997. Treating acute pain in hospital. *Br. Med. J.* 314, 7093 (May 1997), pp. 1531–1535.
- [3] S. M. G. Zwakhalen, J. P. H. Hamers, H. H. Abu-Saad, and M. P. F. Berger. 2006. Pain in elderly people with severe dementia: a systematic review of behavioural pain assessment tools. *BMC Geriatr.* 6, 3 (Jan. 2006), 1–15. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2318-6-3>
- [4] Aisling Ni Thuathail and Claire Welford. 2011. Pain assessment tools for older people with cognitive impairment. *Nurs. Stand.* 26, 6 (Oct. 2011), pp. 39–46. DOI: 10.7748/ns2011.10.26.6.39.c8756
- [5] S. Brahmam, C. F. Chuang, F. Y. Shih, and M. R. Slack. 2006. SVM classification of neonatal facial images of pain. *Fuzzy Log. Appl.* 3849, pp. 121–128. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/11676935_1
- [6] P. Lucey, J. F. Cohn, K. M. Prkachin, P. E. Solomon, S. Chew, and I. Matthews. 2012. Painful monitoring: Automatic pain monitoring using the UNBC-McMaster shoulder pain expression archive database. *Image Vis. Comput.* 30, 3 (Mar. 2012), pp. 197–205. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.imavis.2011.12.003>
- [7] K. Sikka, A. Dhall, and M. S. Bartlett. 2014. Classification and Weakly Supervised Pain Localization using Multiple Segment Representation. *Image Vis. Comput.* 32, 10 (Oct. 2014), pp. 659–670. DOI: 10.1016/j.imavis.2014.02.008
- [8] P. Werner, A. Al-Hamadi, K. Limbrecht-Ecklundt, S. Walter, S. Gruss, and H. C. Traue. 2016. Automatic pain assessment with facial activity descriptors. *IEEE Trans. Affect. Comput.* 99, pp. 1–14.
- [9] L. Colloca, F. Benedetti, and A. Pollo. 2006. Repeatability of autonomic responses to pain anticipation and pain stimulation. *Eur J Pain* 10, 7 (Oct. 2006), pp. 659–665. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejpain.2005.10.009>
- [10] Pietro Cortelli and G. Pierangeli. 2003. Chronic pain-autonomic interactions. *Neurol Sci* 24, (May 2003), pp. 68–70. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s100720300045>
- [11] M. Jeanne, R. Logier, J. De Jonckheere, and B. Tavernier. 2009. Validation of a graphic measurement of heart rate variability to assess analgesia/nociception balance during general anesthesia. In Proceedings of the 31st Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC 2009). IEEE, Minneapolis, MN, pp. 1840–1843. DOI: 10.1109/IEMBS.2009.5332598
- [12] Ilkka Korhonen and Arvi Yli-Hankala. 2009. Photoplethysmography and nociception. *Acta Anaesthesiol Scand* 53, 8 (Sept. 2009), pp. 975–985. DOI: 10.1111/j.1399-6576.2009.02026.x
- [13] T. Ledowski, B. Ang, T. Schmarbeck, and J. Rhodes. 2009. Monitoring of sympathetic tone to assess postoperative pain: skin conductance vs surgical stress index. *Anaesthesia* 64, 7 (July 2009), pp. 727–731. DOI: 10.1111/j.1365-2044.2008.05834.x
- [14] M. L. Loggia, M. Juneau, and M. C. Bushnell. 2011. Autonomic responses to heat pain: heart rate, skin conductance, and their relation to verbal ratings and stimulus intensity. *Pain* 152, 3 (Mar. 2011), pp. 592–598. DOI: 10.1016/j.pain.2010.11.032
- [15] Tanja Schlereth and Frank Birklein. 2008. The sympathetic nervous system and pain. *Neuromolecular Med.* 10, 3 (Sept. 2008), pp. 141–147. DOI: 10.1007/s12017-007-8018-6
- [16] Hanne Storm. 2008. Changes in skin conductance as a tool to monitor nociceptive stimulation and pain. *Curr Opin Anaesthesiol* 21, 6 (Dec. 2008), pp. 796–804. DOI: 10.1097/ACO.0b013e3283183fe4
- [17] Elisabeth Handel (Ed.). 2010. Praxishandbuch ZOPA. Verlag Hans Huber.
- [18] R. Treister, M. Kliger, G. Zuckerman, I. Goor Aryeh, and E. Eisenberg. 2012. Differentiating between heat pain intensities: the combined effect of multiple autonomic parameters. *Pain* 153, 9 (Sept. 2012), pp. 1807–1814. DOI: 10.1016/j.pain.2012.04.008
- [19] J. E. Brown, N. Chatterjee, J. Younger, and S. Mackey. 2011. Towards a physiology-based measure of pain: patterns of human brain activity distinguish painful from non-painful thermal stimulation. *PLoS One* 6, 9 (Sept. 2011), e24124. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0024124>
- [20] S. Gruss, R. Treister, P. Werner, H. C. Traue, S. Crawcour, A. Andrade, and S. Walter. 2015. Pain intensity recognition rates via biopotential feature patterns with support vector machines. *PLoS ONE* 10, 10 (Oct. 2015), e0140330. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0140330>
- [21] S. Walter, S. Gruss, H. Ehleiter, J. Tan, H. C. Traue, S. Crawcour, et al. 2013. The biovid heat pain database data for the advancement and systematic validation of an automated pain recognition system. In Proceedings of 2013 IEEE International Conference on Cybernetics (CYBCONF). IEEE, Lausanne, CH, 128–131. DOI: 10.1109/CYBCONF.2013.6617456
- [22] C. Jensen, O. Vasseljen, and R. H. Westgaard. 1993. The influence of electrode position on bipolar surface electromyogram recordings of the upper trapezius muscle. *Eur. J. Appl. Physiol.* 67, 3 (1993), pp. 266–273.
- [23] Jonghwa Kim and Elisabeth André. 2008. Emotion recognition based on physiological changes in music listening. *IEEE Trans. Pattern Anal. Mach. Intell.* 30, 12 (Feb. 2008), pp. 2067–2083. DOI: 10.1109/TPAMI.2008.26
- [24] A. O. Andrade, P. Kyberd, and S. J. Nasuto. 2008. The application of the Hilbert spectrum to the analysis of electromyographic signals. *Inf Sci* 178, 9 (May 2008), pp. 2176–2193. DOI: 10.1016/j.ins.2007.12.013
- [25] A. O. Andrade, S. J. Nasuto, and P. Kyberd. 2007. Extraction of motor unit action potentials from electromyographic signals through generative topographic mapping. *J Franklin Inst* 344, 3 (July 2007), pp. 154–179.
- [26] A. Kapoor, W. Burleson, and R. W. Picard. 2007. Automatic prediction of frustration. *Int J Hum Comput Stud* 65, 8 (Aug. 2007), pp. 724–736. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijhcs.2007.02.003
- [27] C. Hsu, C. Chang, and C. Lin. 2003. A practical guide to support vector classification. Technical report, Department of Computer Science, National Taiwan University, Taipei, TW.
- [28] Louis M. Rea and Richard A. Parker. 2014. Designing and conducting survey research: a comprehensive guide (4th. ed.). Jossey-Bass, San Francisco, Chapter 4.